

Gourmet Trip: The Instructors' and Professors' Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Gourmet trip means travelling of a food expert for enjoyment via eating and drinking experiences at the destination. The study covered only the point of view of the travelling instructors/professors of Surigao Del Sur State University- Main Campus with side trip for food. There were 61 respondents who composed the total number of permanent instructors/professors of Surigao Del Sur State University- Main Campus. The results of the data come up to the conclusion that travelers love and need food. Also the study found out that gourmet trip had its great potential on tourism market as well as tourism industry. Travelers and tourists are humans, and had the nature to need food and want food. Food is for pleasure seekers and adventure seekers food had its promises. Every individual is a food expert by his/her own taste.

Keywords: *GourmetTrip, Travelers Perspective*

INTRODUCTION

Humans need to eat but nowadays, eating is not only a need to be satisfied but also a want and a hobby in tourism not only to experience the event, see the sites but also to taste and indulge the food culture of the places a tourist visits. Probably most tourists eat and dine out. It allows an individual to savor food cultures while they are on tour. Obviously here in the Philippines almost every locality has its own signature dishes or foods as well as on the other countries. There are tourists who travel for food to taste, and pleasure them while educating themselves as food experts. There is a real need to know from the tourists on what their whims and caprices on food tourism, being the customers. The main purpose of this proposal was to come up with a description of gourmet trip -based form on the tourists' perspective.

Food basically is an integral aspect of the tourist experience. The tourists nowadays indulged not only the sights and sounds, but also the taste of a place. Local food is a fundamental component of a destination's attributes, adding to the range of attractions and the overall tourist experience. This makes food an essential constituent of tourism production as well as consumption. As the World Food Travel Association(2013)say to introduce how food collides with tourism. Food tourism means travelling to seek enjoyment via eating and drinking experiences at the destination. Halland Mitchell (2006) said that, well every living organism always wants to eat and needs to eat for satisfaction and rejuvenate.

In recent years, food has gained recognition by governments, business, and academics as an integral part of the tourism product, and as a means of differentiation for destinations. There are many benefits to be had in linking food and tourism for all stakeholders concerned. Similarly Haven-Tang and Jones in (2006) said that, local food is a vital element that can help create a sense of 'place' and heighten destination appeal. Sims (2009) anticipated that, local produce adds authenticity to the tourist experience and provides motivation for visitors to come to a location. Hall and Mitchell (2006) agreed that, tourists may even be tempted to stay longer in one place because of the availability of food products and related activities. Relating Hashimoto and Telfer(2006) said, increasingly food is used in development initiatives to strengthen tourism destinations, and to create linkages of benefit to both the food production industry and the tourism industry.

Tourism industry in the Philippines is very profitable and yet there is little information on how should traveler's expressed demand on the kind of food they most likely buy while visiting a place away from home. Those who travel and are strangers in a place maybe looking for a specific food taste that long or that one which they want to taste for the first time. Businessmen engages in tourism industry will make it a plus factor if they know reliable data sourced out from a research as to how they could have an edge in tourism business that focuses on food services.

Conceptual Framework

This study was anchored on the concept on the nature of the Filipinos in food festive. It was well noted that Filipinos spent a lot in festivities that highlighted food serving in as extravagance. In cultures like that of the Filipinos where hospitality was important, food tourism was a shining attraction for travelers to be enticed.

Figure1. Schematic Diagram of the study

The focal matter was the travelers. The data they provided gave great meaning to the description of food tourism. The general description of the food tourism industry was specified in the four attributing factors first their general preference on food. It showed how often a traveler do take part in activities while traveling for pleasure: Second general interest on food, this part measured the general interest of the traveler in food: Third was their attitude on food, which will took part of measuring a travels attitude towards food while traveling: Fourth, their interest in food related activity, which will collaborate what travelers as tourist would be entice to visit regarding food related activities. Their whole being was disclosed according to features relevant to the salient points of the study

Perceptions, whims and caprices of the customers were great influence in the viability of the business engagement. Upon the revelation of the travelers' perception, the study proposed a food tourism industry design based on the perceptions of the travelers who were the customers. The schematic diagram showed that a traveler considers four beneficial factors that attracts and magnetize them to travel. Then a tourism based perspective would upshot.

Statement of the Problem

del Sur State University – Main Campus, Tandag City. Specifically, it sights to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the travelers in terms of?
 - 1.1 Sex;
 - 1.2 Age;
 - 1.3 Marital status; and
 - 1.4 Purpose of Travel?
2. What us the level of the respondents' general preferences regarding food when traveling?
3. What is the level of the respondent's general interest in food?
4. What is the level of the respondent's attitude towards food?
5. What is the level of the respondent's interest in food related activities?

METHODOLOGY

This part explains the methods used to address the research questions. First the design is described. The respondent of the study is revealed, and then it's Research Locality Map. The construction of the survey instrument is described next, the data gathering and the statistical treatment.

Research Design

The study was designed to solicit perceptions of respondents in order to describe the variable in its perspective. It was a quantitative research design. A quantitative survey method was in form of investigation that gathered the certain number of data that would eventually present the subject at hand.

Research Respondents

The respondents were the persons who used to travel and describe the food they ate while traveling and indulge the destination. Respondents are instructors of Surigaodel Sur Stated University – Main Campus. They usually travelled for seminars, training and other business transactions in other places. They sometimes had tours in other tourist destination. There were 61

respondents using the stratified random sampling for each College of Surigao Del Sur State University – Main Campus Tandag. instructors were the respondents since it is convenient and accessible for us to conduct our study.

This table represents the names of college, population and samples of the respondents

Table1. Sample Respondents

College	Population	Sample
College of Teachers Education	12	11
College of Arts and Sciences	38	17
College of Business and Management	36	17
College of Engineering, Computer Science Technology	34	16
Total Respondents	120	61

Figure2. Map of SDSSU

The map describes the location of the research respondents in which the survey of the study was conducted. This is where the researchers conducted the study. The route is very accessible because it is located at the National highway Surigao City to Davao City Coastal Road.

Research Instrumentation

An adopted survey questionnaire was used as instrument. There was five parts of the modified adopted Questionnaire from Food Tourism and the culinary tourists by Sajna S. Shenoy (2005). The first part of the survey questionnaire inquired on the profile of the respondents. The second section solicited on the perception of the respondents in form of revelation of their food preferences. Third section asked the respondents on their interest in food. The following section asked the respondents regarding their attitude towards food. The Last section asked the respondents on their interest in food related activities.

Data-gathering Procedure

The researchers secured permission from the administration of SDSSU Main Campus for the survey to be conducted in the campus. Instructors were then approached and were requested to answer the questionnaire. Retrieval of the questionnaire was done as soon as the instructor finished or as they requested to come back for a time. Upon retrieval of the questionnaire the data will be tallied and be submitted to the statistician for analysis.

Statistical Treatments

The first problem was treated with frequency counting and simple percentage. The next three problems used weighted mean. It was measured Farman's 5 point Likert scale.

Parameter

1.0-1.8 – Very Unimportant

1.81-2.6 – Unimportant

2.61-3.4 – Neither Important nor Unimportant

3.41-4.2 – Important

4.21-5.0 – Very Important

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and findings of our analysis with the help of a statistician Mrs. Vanissa Inteligando. This describes the basic information derived from analysis of each variable through descriptive statistics. Also presents the results from analysis using frequency counting, Simple Percentage, and average weighted mean.

Table2. Profile of the Respondents

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Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	29	47.54%
Female	32	52.46%
Total	61	100%

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-29	33	54.10%
30-39	12	19.67%
40-49	6	9.84%
50 and above	10	16.39%
Total	61	100%
Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	25	40.98%
Widowed	1	1.64%
Annulled or Separated	0	0
Single	35	57.38%
Total	61	100%
Purpose of Travel	Frequency	Percentage
Visiting Friends and Relatives	26	19.12%
Conventions, Seminars, Meetings	31	22.79%
Entertainment	8	5.88%
Vacation	27	19.85%
Business	8	5.88%
Outdoor Recreation	9	6.62%
Personal	15	11.03%
Holidays	10	7.35%
Other	2	1.47
Total	136	100%

In Table 1 there is 52.46% female respondent much greater in number than the male respondents with 47.54%, in which 32 Female respondents and 29 male respondents out of 61 respondents. In the ratio of population of instructors female has the greater number. The age that is common on respondents is in the parameter of 20-29 in which it has 29 individuals and it is 54.10% of the respondents.

For the Marital status most of the respondents are single which covered 57.38% of the respondents, in which 35 individuals are involved. For the Purpose of Travel Conventions, Seminars and Meetings has the highest rank as expected with the respondents since they are instructors they attend such events which covered 22.79%.

Table3. Preferences Regarding Food when traveling

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Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Purchase local food at roadside stands.	3.08	Sometimes
2. Eat at restaurants where	3.74	Frequently

locals eat.		
3. At the destination I prepare food unique to the area I am visiting.	3.23	Sometimes
4. Dine at places where food is prepared with respect to local tradition.	3.75	Frequently
5. Dine at restaurants serving distinctive cuisines.	3.61	Frequently
6. Dine at restaurants serving regional specialties.	3.56	Frequently
7. Try or explore local foods.	3.69	Frequently
8. Eat at food festivals	3.48	Frequently
9. Purchase local food products to take back home.	3.62	Frequently
10. Buy cookbooks with local recipes to take back home.	2.72	Sometimes
11. Buy local kitchen equipment to take back home.	2.84	Sometimes
12. Visit a local farmer's market.	2.98	Sometimes
13. Dine at fast food outlets (e.g. McDonald's, Jollibee).	3.75	Frequently
Overall Weighted Mean	3.39	Sometimes

Preference Regarding food when traveling table gets an overall mean 3.39 resulted to sometimes.

Sometimes indicates traveler used to prefer in between. There are travelers that are mid-centric sometimes they try sometimes they don't. The tourist makes their purchasing decision but sometimes they are confused on their decision. Mitchell & Hall (2003)

Highest weighted mean is 3.75 which resulted to frequently. Frequently indicates travelers prefer it often or habitually. Indicators number four and thirteen; dine at places where food is prepared with respect to local tradition; and Dine at fast food outlets (e.g. McDonald's, Jollibee). Traditional foods are tried and tested by time and is sometimes a specialty of the locality. Dining to fast food chains is very convenient. Karim, (2006)

Lowest weighted mean 2.72 which resulted to some times. Sometimes indicates travelers who use to prefer

in between. Indicators number ten; Buy cookbooks with local recipes to take back home. Buying cookbooks nowadays is expensive and they prefer browsing the internet, because of the advance technology books are uploaded in the internet. Another thing is that buying cookbook is time consuming when traveling for important matters. Murray (2011)

Table4. The Respondents General Interest in Food.

Table 4. The Respondents General Interest in Food.		
Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. When I eat out, I like to try the most unusual items, even if I am not sure I would like them.	3.39	Unsure
2. While preparing foods or snacks, I like to try new recipes.	3.84	Agree
3. I think it is fun to try out food items I am not familiar with.	3.67	Agree
4. I am eager to know what kind of foods people from other countries eat.	3.97	Agree
5. I like to eat exotic foods.	2.89	Unsure
6. Items on the menu that I am unfamiliar with, make me curious.	3.61	Agree
7. I prefer to eat food products that I am used to.	4.07	Agree
8. I am curious about food products that I am not familiar with.	3.80	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.66	Agree

The Respondents general interest in food gets an overall mean weighted 3.67 as agree. Agree indicates that travelers are interested or attracted to it. Human race needs food, so as the traveler not only basic need but interested as a hobby. Tourist seeks to explore food from local or ethnic regions. Hall, (2004)

Highest weighted mean is 4.07 resulted to Agree. Indicators number seven; I prefer to eat food products that I am used to. Agree indicates that travelers are interested or attracted to it. A familiar food to an

individual is commonly consumed because they are already comfortable to it and products that has already established a name in the industry. Frochot (2003).

Lowest weighted mean is 2.89 resulted to Unsure. Unsure indicates that travelers are undecided regarding to what food they will eat. Indicators number five; I like to eat exotic foods. However some of the travelers are psycho centric means sticking to what they are used to. They find familiar foods as comfortable for them and they visit or purchase food that is already well known or a signature for the place. Telfer& Hashimoto (2003), Mitchell & Hall (2003)

Table5. The Respondents Attitude towards Food

Table 5. The Respondents Attitude towards Food		
Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. I am constantly trying new and different foods.	3.66	Agree
2. I am very particular about the foods I will eat.	4.11	Agree
3. I will eat almost anything.	3.30	Unsure
4. I like to try new ethnic restaurants.	3.62	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.67	Agree

The Respondents attitude towards Food gets overall mean resulted also to agree. Agree indicates the travelers most likely to explore and try new foods that are innovative. This shows that most of the travelers specifically the instructors are allocentric which means they like to explore. Trying and tasting new foods is like indulging the taste of the locality. Ignatov and Smith (2006) as cited by Mason and O'Mahony (2007).

Highest weighted mean is 4.11 resulted Agree indicator number two; I am very particular about the foods I will eat. Agree indicates the travelers most likely to explore and try new foods that are innovative. Travelers specifically instructors chooses food that they perceive as acceptable and safe for their health. As cited by Muntean et al., (2010).

Lowest weighted mean is 3.30 which resulted to Unsure indicator number 3; I will eat almost anything. Unsure indicates that travelers are doubtful regarding to what food they will eat. Travelers specifically

instructors chooses food that they perceive as acceptable and safe for their health. As cited by Mason and O'Mahony (2007).

Table6. The Respondents Interest in Food Related activities

Table 6. The Respondents Interest in Food Related activities		
Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. I have little or no interest in activities related to food.	2.75	Unsure
2. Participating in activities related to food is one of the most enjoyable things I do.	3.72	Agree
3. Participating in activities related to food is very important to me.	3.69	Agree
4. Participating in activities related to food is one of the most satisfying things I do.	3.66	Agree
5. I find a lot of my life is organized around activities related to food.	3.72	Agree
6. Participating in activities related to food occupies a central role in my life.	3.62	Agree
7. I enjoy discussing activities related to food, with my friends.	3.90	Agree
8. I enjoy free food tasting events.	4.00	Agree
9. When I'm participating in activities related to food, I don't have to be concerned with the way I look.	3.31	Unsure
10. I love to visit a place during festivals to taste the different delicacy of a country or place and locality.	3.89	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.63	Agree

The Respondents Interest in food related activities its overall mean 3.63 resulted to agree. Agree indicates had interest regarding food tourism that relates on food activities. Most of the respondents are interested in food related activities. Maybe they are not just focused on teaching but also indulging the culture of the place. Murray had reported in (2011).

Highest weighted 4.0 resulted to Agree indicator number eight; I enjoy free food tasting events. Agree indicates had interest regarding food tourism that relates on food activities. Being human we don't only need basically food but nowadays we enjoy food as a hobby such as food tasting especially free food tasting. Food tasting as cited by Mason & O'Mahony (2007).

The lowest weighted mean 2.75 which resulted to unsure indicator number one; I have little or no interest in activities related to food. Unsure indicates that travelers are doubtful that they had little or no interest on food related activities. This is the lowest that's for the fact that food is our fundamental need. Mitchell & Hall (2003)

CONCLUSION

1. In conclusion, the female sex had the greater number of respondents, which the most of the respondents also are single and in the age 20 to 29. As the respondents are the instructors' conventions, seminars and meetings got the highest rank in the purpose of travel.
2. The researchers concluded that the respondents' preference may consider some factors such as health, safety and acceptable foods.
3. Travelers had the natural interest in food related activities which means, they are the best experts to say Food is a marketable business in tourism because travelers are gourmets.
4. It has been concluded that the respondents are willing to travel for food, they are willing to travelers had the interest on what food would be explore foods that are unique yet acceptable to what they prefer and comfortable with.
5. Most instructors and professors are gourmets who are willing to spend for food activities such as enjoying food tasting in festivals and to taste food delicacies of the locality while educating themselves at the destination.

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